

ISSUES OF EFFECTIVE ORGANIZATION OF EDUCATIONAL WORK TO EDUCATE STUDENTS IN THE NATIONAL SPIRIT THROUGH MUSIC

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada musiqa orqali o‘quvchilarni milliy va umuminsoniy g‘oyalar asosida tarbiyalash, dunyoqarashini kengaytirish, musiqiy didini o‘stirish kabi bugungi kun uchun dolzarb masalalarga amaliy tavsiyalar va takliflar bayon etilgan.

Kalit so‘zlar: Mumtoz musiqa, axloq, ta‘lim-tarbiya, interfaol metodlar, estetik did, his tuyg‘u, an‘anaviy bayramlar, milliy qadriyatlar.

Аннотация: В данной статье представлены практические рекомендации и предложения по актуальным вопросам, таким как музыкальное воспитание школьников на основе национальных и общечеловеческих идей, расширение кругозора, развитие музыкального вкуса.

Ключевые слова: Классическая музыка, мораль, образование, интерактивные методы, эстетический вкус, чувство, традиционные праздники, национальные ценности.

Abstract: In this article, practical recommendations and suggestions are presented for current issues such as education of students through music based on national and universal ideas, broadening of worldview, development of musical taste.

Key words: Classical music, morality, education, interactive methods, aesthetic taste, feeling, traditional holidays, national values.

Instilling the essence of the national spirit in teenage students through music songs on various topics and materials specified in the music program and textbooks tunes serve as an important resource. The types of activities related to musical education include, first of all, parents of students in the family, helping their children acquire musical knowledge, social protection of children, being able to choose students with musical talents and so on working with, in the process of training, folk classical musical heritage, musical instruments. There are activities such as training

to work with teaching musical literacy for the use of advanced pedagogical technologies and a technological approach is required in the education of the national psyche. In the process of research, it is defined in the program and expressed in textbooks from the topics, the topics related to the education of the national spirit were separated and special lessons was established. From interactive methods and traditional forms of lessons lessons conducted with students using their music formation of thinking, worldview, musical imagination, feeling, aesthetic taste together with the nation's internal state, experiences, feelings of character, spiritual world, thoughts, goals and occupations, moods and unique they were also able to get acquainted with its features.

It is known that the educational process has its own characteristics, it takes a long time, complex and requires continuity. Because the student is not yet fully formed because of this, the teacher's activity takes the main place. Accordingly, education technology differs from educational technology. Education technology and its components O‘.Q. Tolipov and M.Usmonboeva defines as follows:

- 1) the general project of the educational process;
- 2) social need (incentive) to organize education;
- 3) purpose of education;
- 4) content of education (form, method, method and technical means);
- 5) activity of a teacher (educator);
- 6) student (student) activity;
- 7) educational effect (result).

So, technologicalization of the educational process has a specific purpose and is social based on the idea and to form spiritual and moral qualities in students is the organizational and technical organization of directed pedagogical activity Rephonologization of the educational process is different from the educational process the result cannot be seen in the short term. Accordingly, the process of education requires a new approach to technology.

Eastern thinkers and the people in the education of the national spirit in students based on the experiences of music pedagogy. In this regard, the national spirit the purpose, tasks of education, formation of national consciousness and behavior is carried out in the course of directed activity. In general, personal education, including spiritual education, is exclusively private It is not a work, but a social national work. Because the power of each state, The development of the people depends on the education of the generations. Pedagogically correct student activities

in the process of educational work organization is very important. Accordingly, teachers organize children's activities not limited to reaching, their events related to this activity, various how he perceives, evaluates, feels experiences, what he gets from them it is important that he knows what he is getting.

In the process of educational work, it is important to develop not only the student's mind, but also his feelings, and the moral values that the society imposes on the individual. It is also necessary to develop the necessary moral skills and habits. In this process, the teacher determines the students' activities, their goals influencing the student's mind, feelings and will to be educated accordingly goes It creates conditions for students to participate in the social process.

Students' independence and creativity through active participation in educational work initiative increases. The activity is for the purposeful interest of students and if it is organized on the basis of desire, the intended goal can be achieved. If the student if he feels responsible for his behavior, it is educational work becomes an active participant. In order to effectively train the national spirit, he It is necessary to know well the source of the driving force of the educational process.

The skills and habits formed in the course of activity are the education of the national spirit eases compliance with the criteria. So, the period of intensive development of the educator child's personality is schooling In his years, various activities came to his mind - study, work, social work, play, sports, art it is important to have a special effect with the help of amateurism, including music. It is known that education is carried out in a holistic process, and its components are the same at the same time, it appears on the basis of some type of activity. Therefore, it is established goals and tasks are not random, but predetermined and carefully thought out will be decided on the basis of plans. Including in the process of educating the national spirit the purpose, forms and methods of education have an important place. Educational the content of work is determined on the basis of the order of the social system and its implementation certain conditions are required. It is known that in the organization of educational work, it is related to the education of the national spirit events are of particular importance. The forms of such events are diverse, none of them is complete without music, as well as different forms of education It is important to choose event forms depending on the content, essence, and significance of the event. In this regard, the educational institution's conditions, possibilities,

musical and technical the availability and adjustment of tools, the status of the students' amateur club is important in choosing the form of the educational event.

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